

Ideas of Special Relativity in Newtonian Mechanics?

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The purpose of this note is to ask: Why isn't energy sufficient for describing a particle? Why does one need momentum? We suggest that the answer is related to the notion of conservation of energy (a number) and momentum, a vector, in the case of a two body collision and that this should be fundamentally present in special relativity which means that the seemingly independent Newtonian idea of action-reaction should also be present in special relativity.

The Case of Momentum

Momentum is introduced in Newtonian mechanics as:

$p = m_0 v$, where m_0 is rest mass and v is the vector velocity ((1))

Momentum then appears in Newton's second law: $dp/dt = \text{Force}(x)$ and is key to the Newtonian framework, but why does it appear in the first place? Why isn't energy sufficient for describing a particle? For example, a rest mass requires a force to make it move. It represents an impedance to movement. A force must act on it for some time/distance to move it from a speed of $v=0$ to v . This may be associated with the loose idea of work or energy. An interaction may be described by a force with distance and time and energy. Why should there be a momentum vector? We try to consider this in two different ways. The first is linked to special relativity and the second to conservation of energy and momentum.

Considerations from Special Relativity

Consider a particle at rest at $x=0$ with rest mass m_0 and time t . A moving frame (with $-v$ constant) sees the particle move with v , such that $x'/t' = v$. At first glance, one might argue that $t'=t$, but clearly $x' \neq x$. If this is the case, time and space are treated differently and one does not require a matrix transformation. X' presumably describes the center-of-mass co-ordinate. If one considers that a particle which moves has received some work and should have some energy, then one has m_0 in the rest frame, and $E(m_0, v)$ in the moving.

This is the opposite scheme from the $x', t'=t$ one because in the rest frame one has m_0, t , but then argues that $m_0 \rightarrow E$ while $t=t'$.

If one wishes to make the schemes equivalent, due to the invariance of frames moving with constant speed relative to each other, then one is forced to adopt a 2×2 matrix scheme linking (x, ct) with (x', ct') and t cannot equal t' . The same matrix may link $m_0, 0$ and $E(m_0, v), p$ because both transformations are due to the movement of the origin in the moving frame picture. Then, one has the matrix transformation:

$$\begin{vmatrix} \gamma(v/c) & \gamma(v/c) \\ \gamma(v/c) & \gamma(v/c) \end{vmatrix} \quad ((2))$$

Invariance of motion in frames relative to each other suggests an invariance equation linking (x', ct') with (x, ct) and $(0, m_0 c)$ with (pc, E) . One already sees that Newton's momentum $p = mv$ may be directly linked to this transformation and plays the same roles as $x = ct$, i.e. $p = E v$.

An invariant quantity from linear algebra is the modulus, i.e. a dot product under a certain metric (usually $xx + yy + zz = rr$), for matrices which represent a kind of rotation. Given that one knows a priori that one requires an invariance equation, it seems that one should consider the one provided by linear algebra, albeit with the correct metric. Thus:

$$-E^2 + p^2 c^2 = -m_0^2 c^4 \quad ((3))$$

and $E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$, $p = mv / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ (one dimension)

For $v \ll c$, one obtains the usual Newtonian kinetic energy $KE = .5mv^2$ correction to $m_0 c^2$ and $p = mv$, so this seems to show how momentum appears.

These ideas, however, seem to be already known in the literature, i.e. in the theory of special relativity. The question we wish to consider here is: Why does one need momentum in the first place? Is it simply a mathematical function which allows one to create an invariance equation, i.e. ((3))? If one considers a particle at rest with rest mass m_0 , then it is fine for it to appear to be moving as seen from a frame moving with constant $-v$, but physically one knows that a force must be applied to m_0 for some time and distance to make it move. This suggests that some "work" is done to the particle and one no longer talks of m_0 , but of $E(m_0, v)$. Similarly, a moving particle requires a force to stop it over distance and time and this seems to be linked with negative work. One may consider a moving particle compressing a spring and then being pushed out again with velocity as demonstrating this idea. Thus, energy is physical and is linked to an interaction, but what is momentum? In the special relativistic case, one creates a vector with p and $E(v)$. $E(v)$ has been argued to be linked to interaction, but why is p needed to describe an interaction?

The Notion of Conservation of Energy and Momentum

We have tried to argue above that one does not physically need the notion of momentum as energy describes an interaction sufficiently. Here, we consider a possible counter-example. Imagine two particles, with the same energy, rest mass and opposite momenta, which collide. The kinetic portions of energy may be converted into sound, heat etc and so even though work is done on each particle, changing its energy from E to $m_0 c^2$, particle E is not conserved as it is a number, i.e. one originally has $2E$ and finally, $2m_0 c^2$. Now, the momentum of the particles is $mv / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ and $-mv / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ and after the collision, each particle is at rest and so the momentum is also 0, even if sound and heat are created. Thus, momentum may be a conserved variable in an interaction which has equal and opposite forces.

These ideas were already known by Newton and so he used both energy and momentum. Energy and momentum, however, emerge naturally as two separate quantities from special relativity. We suggest that one requires two entities, a number (energy) and a vector (momentum) due to conservation in an interaction. We argue that special relativity (or the invariance of frames moving at constant speed relative to each other) seems to be directly

linked to these conservation ideas. The point, however, is that p and E emerge for a single particle in special relativity and not a two body collision.

The question then seems to be: Does conservation of momentum and energy emerge independently of special relativity. One may argue a priori that total energy is conserved, but one might not be so sure of conservation of momentum. In Newtonian mechanics, one has the second law $dp/dt = F$ so for F and $-F$ (Newton's action-reaction also missing from special relativity if one only considers moving frames), $dp_1 = -dp_2$, but there is no Newton's second law in the special relativistic formulation, even though the consequences of work (i.e. kinetic energy) appear in the $v \ll c$ limit. Thus, work as a consequence of interaction is present and if one wishes this to be conserved and linked to interaction, one might expect that p must also be linked to interaction and conserved. As noted, however, p is a vector and so its addition is very different from that of the number E . In fact, given that E is a number, it shows the work that was done on the particle regardless of the actual force-time-distance history it underwent. $P = Ev/c$ carries this same E information multiplied by the velocity vector so it is like a rate or flux expression. One may have $E_1 \neq E_2$, but $p_1 = p_2$. p carries information about the work-energy and how it moves through space-time (described by velocity). Why should this be of interest?

Consider a physical problem of a potential $V(x)$ which does not change in time. Using the ideas of kinetic energy as a quantity (number) in $v \ll c$ case,

$$\Delta KE + \Delta V = 0 \quad ((4))$$

Here the expression for KE follows from the $v \ll c$ limit of $m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ and not Newtonian mechanics and ((4)) is a conservation of energy equation. At the same time, work is done by a force in a little dx , but the time available for the work is $dt = dx/v$.

$$dKE = m_0 v dv \quad (v \ll c) \text{ so: } m_0 v dv = -dV \rightarrow m_0 dv = -dV dt/dx = (dV/dx) dt \quad ((5))$$

By using an energy conservation equation ((4)), an expression involving momentum naturally emerges:

$$dp/dt = -dV/dx \quad \text{for } v \ll c \quad ((6))$$

In a two particle collision, one may argue that $-dV/dx$ acting on one particle is equivalent to dV/dx acting on the other, i.e. Newton's action-reaction. Then:

$$d/dt (p_1 + p_2) = 0 \quad ((7)) \text{ or conservation of momentum emerges.}$$

((7)) seems to hold even for the case the particle energy is not conserved as long as total energy is. Thus, the idea of E and p being linked with conservation seems to be fundamental and can be obtained starting directly from special relativity $v \ll c$, assuming energy conservation a priori and using Newton's concept of action-reaction.

The question then becomes: Why does one have to introduce action-reaction independently from special relativity in order to see conservation of energy and momentum. Furthermore, we

assumed conservation of energy a priori in order to obtain conservation of momentum. We have argued that both should appear naturally from special relativity, which introduces E and p in the first place. In the above discussion, we started with the $v \ll c$ special relativistic form of KE and a priori energy conservation and obtained an expression for momentum as well as its conservation if action-reaction (an independent idea) holds. Special relativity, however, gives E and p on the same footing and it seems it should also give a conservation form for both. This means that special relativity should contain the idea of action-reaction inherently, it seems.

We have argued in previous notes that it does, but only if one considers $-Et+px = \text{constant}$ as having degenerate solutions:

$$T \text{ and } t+n\hbar/E \quad \text{and } x \text{ and } x+n\hbar/p \quad ((8))$$

This leads to a periodic pattern described by $\exp(-iEt)\exp(ipx)$ which gives the sense of action-reaction and conservation of energy and momentum:

$$\text{Integral } \exp(iE_1t)\exp(-iE_2t) dt = 0 \text{ if } E_1 \neq E_2 \quad ((9a)) \text{ and } \text{Integral } dx \exp(-ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x) = 0 \text{ unless } p_1=p_2 \quad ((9b))$$

In other words, special relativity yields both E and p and it seems that one does not really need p unless one links both it and E to independent conservation forms which may be used to describe interactions.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we ask: Why does special relativity yield two interaction variables: E (energy, number) and p (momentum, vector)? Energy seems to carry the information of the work needed to change $v=0$ to v and seems to be a naturally conserved quantity. On the other hand, it is not clear what p is, if one does not know Newtonian physics. It is simply a math vector which seems to appear. If, however, E is linked with interaction and is conserved, one would expect the same for p , as both appear in the same 4-vector. We have shown that starting with conservation of energy and action-reaction, one may obtain both an expression for p and its conservation in the $v \ll c$ case. Special relativity, however, creates E and p a priori and so it seems it should provide for the possibility of their independent conservations. This, however, requires a notion of action-reaction (which Newton discussed, but does not seem to appear a priori in special relativity which is linked with invariance of frames moving at constant speeds to each other). We suggest, as we have before, that there must be a kind of action-reaction present in special relativity and argue that it is in fact the free particle quantum mechanical $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ which then directly leads to conservation of energy and momentum following ((9))